

Synthesis and Biological Screening of Some Oxadiazolyl/Triazolyl/Thiadiazolyl Benzimidazoles

ANIL K. SENGUPTA and MADHURI GOYAL*

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226 007

Manuscript received 5 November 1982, accepted 30 May 1983

Some S-(2-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)/S-(3-aryloxymethyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-2-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles (IIa) and S-(2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-2-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles (IIb) have been synthesised. All of them were screened for their antibacterial activity and only five of them for antiacetylcholinesterase activity *in vitro*. They show fairly high antibacterial activity but only marginal inhibition of acetylcholinesterase activity.

BENZIMIDAZOLES substituted with various moieties have been reported as effective bactericides¹, fungicides² and pesticides³. We have reported⁴ synthesis and biological activities of S-(2-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)/S-(3-aryloxymethyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-2-mercaptoacetic acids (Ia). As an extension of this work, the synthesis and biological screening of S-(2-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)/S-(3-aryloxymethyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles (IIa) and S-(2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-2-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles (IIb) have been carried out.

Benzimidazoles (IIa and IIb) have been synthesised⁵ by the reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine and S-(2-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)/S-(3-aryloxymethyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-2-mercaptoacetic acids (Ia) and S-(2-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-2-mercaptoacetic acids⁴ (Ib), respectively in 4*N* HCl solution. All the compounds have been characterised by tlc, ir and elemental analysis. The newly synthesised compounds exhibited in their ir spectra characteristic absorption bands at 3300 (>N-H), 1520 (>C=N-, cyclic), 1250 (>N-N=C cyclic) and 1360 cm⁻¹ (pentacyclic ring).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS IIa (1-9) AND IIb (10-13)

Compd. No.	R	X	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula
1.	2-OH ₃	O	200	48	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S
2.	4-OH ₃	O	154	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S
3.	4-Cl	O	180	54	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₂ S
4.	2,4-di-Cl	O	163	52	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₂ S
5.	3-OH ₃	N-C ₆ H ₅	188	45	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ OS
6.	4-OH ₃	N-C ₆ H ₅	122	46	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ OS
7.	4-Cl	N-C ₆ H ₅	156	50	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ OS
8.	4-CH ₃	N-C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ _p	189	50	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ OS
9.	4-Cl	N-C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ _p	173	48	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ ClN ₄ OS
10.	H	S	118	45	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂
11.	4-OH ₃	S	195	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂
12.	4-Cl	S	227	52	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ S ₂
13.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	S	186	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ OS ₂

Satisfactory O, H and N analyses have been obtained for all the compounds.

S-(2-Aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)-2-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles (IIa, 1-4): A mixture of S-(2-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)-2-mercaptoacetic acid (Ia) and *o*-phenylenediamine was refluxed in 4*N* HCl for 10 hr. After cooling, the

1 = *o*-phenylenediamine
X = O, N-aryl, S
R = 2-OH₃; 3-OH₃; 4-OH₃; 4-Cl; 2,4-di-Cl; 4-OC₂H₅

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR were recorded on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

reaction mixture was filtered and made alkaline with ammonia solution. The residue thus obtained was crystallised from aqueous acetic acid (Table I).

S-(3-Aryloxymethyl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles (IIa, 5-9) and S-(2-arylamino-

* Present Address: Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007.

1,3,4-thiadiazol-5-yl)-2-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles (IIb, 10-13) were synthesised similarly (Table 1).

Biological activities: All the reported compounds were evaluated for their bactericidal activity⁶ against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus subtilis* *in vitro* and only five (compd. 1, 3, 4, 7, 8) of them were tested^{7,8} against acetylcholinesterase enzyme *in vitro* according to the methods described earlier. The results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL, AND ANTIACETYLCHOLINESTERASE ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS IIa AND IIb

Compd. No.	Antibacterial activity ¹			Antiacetylcholinesterase activity at 8.8×10^{-4} M concentration	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	Percent inhibition	$I_{50}^{2,3}$ 1×10^{-4} M
1.	+	-	-	21.54	8.8
2.	+++	-	++	—	—
3.	++	-	-	88.08	2.1
4.	+++	+++	-	99.70	1.9
5.	+++	+++	-	—	—
6.	++	++	-	—	—
7.	-	+++	+++	85.10	2.2
8.	++	++	-	22.54	8.4
9.	++	+++	-	—	—
10.	+	-	++	—	—
11.	+	-	-	—	—
12.	++	+++	++	—	—
13.	+++	-	++	—	—

1. — = no inhibition; + = zone size 6-8 mm; ++ = zone size 9-14 mm; +++ = zone size 15-20 mm.

2. I_{50} value is the concentration of the compound which causes 50% inhibition of enzyme activity.

3. I_{50} value for neostigmine, a potent antiacetylcholinesterase inhibitor used as standard in similar conditions is 1.96×10^{-7} M.

Almost all the compounds have shown activity against *S. aureus*. Triazolyl benzimidazoles (compd. 5 to 9) are more active against *B. pumilus* as compared to the rest of the compounds. The growth of *B. subtilis* has not been inhibited markedly by these compounds. The five benzimidazoles tested against the enzyme acetylcholinesterase have only marginal activity although chlorosubstitution in compd. 3, 4 and 7 has increased the percentage inhibition of the enzyme.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow for facilities and Mr. F. A. Khan for enzyme activity assay. One of the authors (M.G.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. M. HAMADA and M. ARAKAWA, *Chem. Abs.* 1979, **90**, 67704.
2. S. D. SINGH and S. M. P. NAIK, *Pesticides*, 1977, **11**, 49; *Chem. Abs.*, 1977, **86**, 166262.
3. S. Z. ABO, *Chem. Abs.*, 1979, **90**, 38918.
4. A. K. SENGUPTA and M. GARG, *J. Antibact. Antifung. Agents.*, Communicated.
5. M. A. PHILLIPS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2393.
6. R. S. VERMA and S. A. IMAM, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1973, **13**, 45.
7. S. HESTRIN, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1949, **180**, 249.
8. S. P. COLWICK and N. O. KAPLAN, "Methods in Enzymology", Academic Press, New-York.